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ASSESSMENT OF THE HEALTH STATUS, POSSIBLE INFECTION OF THE BODY OF STUDENTS WITH HELICOBACTER PYLORI AND THEIR AWARENESS

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Annotation: The assessment of the health status, possible infection of the organism of students of higher educational institutions and students of secondary educational institutions of *Helicobacter pylori* and their awareness of it was carried out. As a result of the study, it was found that 35 % (78 respondents) have a history of gastritis/ulcer. One of the reasons for the development of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract in young students is non-compliance with the diet due to lack of time.

Keywords: students, health, awareness, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract

ОЦЕНКА СТАТУСА ЗДОРОВЬЯ, ВОЗМОЖНОГО ИНФИЦИРОВАНИЯ ОРГАНИЗМА УЧАЩЕЙСЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ HELICOBACTER PYLORI И ИХ ИНФОРМИРОВАННОСТИ

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Аннотация: Проведена оценка статуса здоровья, возможного инфицирования организма студентов высших учебных заведений и учащихся средних учебных заведений *Helicobacter pylori* и их информированности о нем. В результате проведенного исследования установлено, что у 35 % (78 респондентов) в анамнезе имеется гастрит/язва. Одной из причин развития заболеваний желудочно-кишечного тракта у учащейся молодежи является несоблюдение режима питания в связи с нехваткой времени.

Ключевые слова: студенты, здоровье, информированность, заболевания желудочно-кишечного тракта

Relevance. The relevance of studying health disorders associated with infection of the body with *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) is not in doubt today. Almost every second inhabitant of the planet is a carrier of *H. pylori*. At the same time, despite the success of laboratory diagnostics, it is not always possible to detect this infection at the early stages of the development of pathologies. Therefore, it is relevant and important to improve the quality of human life to assess the status of his health and infection with *H. pylori* [1-3].

The average prevalence of *H. pylori* infection worldwide is about 50 %, with the highest prevalence in developing countries (80-90 %) and a lower level in Western Europe (30-50 %), North America (30-40 %) and Australia (20 %). The question remains open of selecting the optimal non-invasive technique for the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection, which could serve for remote control of radiation, given the possibility of early reinfection in families [5].

Currently, the problem of clarifying the role of *H. pylori* infection in the pathogenesis of chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease remains urgent, as well as the search for an optimal differentiated approach in the primary diagnosis of infection, identification of clinical features and effective methods of treatment, as well as prevention of diseases associated with infection of the body with *H. pylori*. Many medical professionals in their practice strive to adhere to a strictly individual approach when choosing a particular method of *H. pylori* treatment [6].

Goal. Assessment of the health status, possible infection of the organism of students of higher educational institutions and students of secondary educational institutions of *H. pylori* and their awareness of it.

The objectives of the study included:

- 1) to study the theoretical and methodological aspects of the topic under study;
- 2) get an idea of the main features of *H. pylori*;
- 3) determine the level of awareness of students and students about this disease;
- 4) make recommendations on the prevention of the main complications of infection with *H. Pylori*.

Materials and methods of research. The paper uses the method of sociological survey by anonymous voluntary questionnaire. The obtained data were processed statistically.

In March 2022, a survey was conducted on the statistical assessment of the health of students of secondary and higher educational institutions, in which 223 respondents (96 college students and 127 university students) took part.

140 girls (62.8 %) and 83 boys (37.2 %) took part in the survey. Age range: <18 – 47 (21,1 %); 18-19 years – 111 (49.9 %); 20-21 years – 56 (25,1 %); >21 – 9 (4 %).

All participants were asked the following questions:

1. Your age?
2. Your gender?
3. Are you a student or a student of a secondary educational institution?
4. Is there/ has there been a history of gastritis/ulcer?
5. Do you have an infection of the body with *H. pylori* before?
6. Does your relatives have an infection of the organism with *H. pylori*?
7. Do you know about the ways of *H. pylori* transmission?
8. Are you familiar with the methods of diagnosing *H. pylori* infection?
9. Are you familiar with the methods of preventing infection of the body with *H. pylori*?
10. Do you know the role of *H. pylori* in the pathogenesis of chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease?

11. Do you know the methods of diagnosis of gastric ulcer?

12. Are you familiar with the methods of prevention of gastric ulcer?

Results and their discussion. During the survey, it was found out that 35 % (78 people) of respondents have gastrointestinal tract diseases and 65 % (145 people) do not.

It was found that 9.4 % (21 people) of respondents had a previous history of infection with *H. pylori*: 52.5 % (117 people) did not have it; 38.1 % (85 people) did not know.

It was shown that 19.7 % (44 respondents) had relatives infected with *H. pylori*. 80.3 % (179 people) were not infected.

Known methods of transmission of *H. pylori* 37.2 % (83 people); unknown – 62.8 % (140 respondents).

The main methods of diagnosing the presence of *H. Pylori* in the body are known – 31.8 % (71 respondents); not known – 68.2 % (152 people).

Are you familiar with the methods of preventing *H. infection? pylori* – 35.9 % (80 respondents); unknown – 65.1 % (143 people). 18.4 % (41 respondents) know about the role of *H. pylori* in the pathogenesis of chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease; 81.6 % (182 people) do not know.

Methods of diagnosis of gastric ulcer are known – 30 % (67 respondents); not known – 70 % (156 people). 55.1 % (123 respondents) are familiar with the methods of prevention of gastric ulcer; 44.8 % (100 people) are not familiar.

Conclusions. Thus, as a result of the conducted research, it was found that 35 % (78 respondents) have a history of gastritis/ulcer. One of the reasons for the development of gastrointestinal diseases in young students is non-compliance with the diet due to lack of time.

It was shown that when one of the family members was infected with *H. pylori* in 14 cases out of 44, the respondents also had this infection, which was 31.8 %. Some respondents (40.9 % or 18 people) found it difficult to answer this question and only 20.3 % (12 respondents) gave a negative answer. The results obtained indicate that *H. pylori* infection often occurs within a family or other closely communicating groups.

A low degree of awareness of students about the basic methods of diagnosis, treatment and prevention of *H. pylori* infection was revealed. To

increase the level of knowledge of students and students, we have developed a booklet.

The low interest of young people in the prevention of peptic ulcer disease, which is widespread among the adult population, has been established. Therefore, educational institutions need to strengthen their efforts to increase the level of knowledge among young students on this issue.

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